

Rainfall Variability and Extreme Precipitation Trends in Mumbai (2010–2019): A Statistical Analyses Using R Programming

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ABSTRACT

As a coastal city, Mumbai experiences intense southeast monsoon rainfall from June to September. Monsoon rainfall variability, its extreme events as well as rainfall trends are important for climate change adaption, flood studies and planning of water sources. In the present study daily 10 years rainfall data (from 2010 to 2019) is used. The data is collected form Indian Meteorological Department. We have used R programming for rainfall data statistical analyses. We have implemented Mann-Kendal test, moving average with 5 years and extreme events. It is implemented to assess the seasonal patterns, inter-annual variability, and climate change indicators. The obtained result shows moderate inter-annual variability. There is no significant long-term trend total annual rainfall. It also shows increase in extreme rainfall events and monsoon intensity fluctuations. The result indicates need for flood management strategies, urban water management in relation to the rising high intensity rainfall event frequency in Mumbai.

Key words: *Rainfall variability, extreme rainfall events, climate change indicators, monsoon trends, Mann-Kendall test and R programming*

1. Introduction

Mumbai is one of the largest metropolitan cities in India. The city experiences a tropical monsoon driven seasonal rainfall which significantly impact its infrastructure, water resources and disaster management. Therefore, understanding of rainfall variability, extreme rainfall events and rainfall trends over longer period of time is very important for effective flood management and climate change management. In this study we have analysed daily rainfall data for one decade i.e., from 2010 to 2019. The data is obtained from Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) to carry out analyses on rainfall variability, seasonal pattern in rainfall, and climate change indicators. Analyses carried out with R programming language. The analyses include rainfall trend analyses, descriptive statistics, Mann-

Kendall trend test and moving average with 5 years. The analyses detected changes in monsoon intensity, extreme rainfall events and inter-annual variability. We aimed to get insights into rainfall trends. This can be used for climate change adaptation, urban runoff management, and water resources in the hinterland of Mumbai.

2. Rainfall in Mumbai

The rainfall in the Mumbai is very seasonal due to monsoonal characteristics. The intense rainfall occurs in June to September. In Mumbai, some year receives extreme rainfall leads to monsoon flood and water logging, and some year receives below average rainfall. Four-month monsoon rainfall contributes more than 90 percent of the total rainfall. The extreme rainfall events recently increased. The rainfall distribution has become erratic. This suggests shift in monsoon rainfall intensity and variability. This also suggests climate change and effect of the urbanization. The understanding of rainfall pattern is very important for urban city planning.

3. R programming software for rainfall analyses

The R programming software is very powerful tool for daily rainfall analyses for longer period of time. It provides framework for temporal variability analyses, trend detection and to detect the climate change. It provides facility for pre-processing i.e., treatment to missing values, data formatting, and detection of the outliers. Statistical analyses i.e., descriptive statistics, trend analyses, linear regression, can be very easily implemented in R programming language. In addition to this moving average, seasonality analyses can detect long term rainfall pattern. The visualization in R programming can be done with ggplot2 package. This provides graphical visualization of daily, monthly and annual rainfall trend. This helps detail interpretation. Machine learning libraries provide prediction of the trends for future planning. The software is open source and has large community support, which is why it is best choice for such kind of data analyses. The software can handle large data, there is automation in the analyses of workflow, and this data can also be integrated with GIS for spatial analyses. That is why R has emerged as important tools for studies like present study.

4. Aims and Objectives

We aimed in the present study firstly, to analyses rainfall variability and extreme rainfall event from 2010 to 2019 in Mumbai. This will carry out with descriptive statistics, coefficient of variation to assess the inter-seasonal and inter-annual variability. Secondly, to identify long-term trend analyses with climate change indicator with Mann-Kendall trend analyses with five year moving average. This will help to understand changes in monsoon onset, its intensity and duration. And thirdly, to make comprehensive use of R programming language for data pre-processing, data modelling and data visualization in the context of rainfall analyses study.

There are some researches carried out on monsoon variability, high extreme rainfall event and climate change in India. There are limited studies carried out on decadal scale with high resolution daily rainfall data. Many studies are focussed on annual and seasonal trends, but limited studies examined short duration rainfall which is significant in urban flooding. Globally climate model shows increase in monsoon variability, local studies show trends analyses and machine learning based predictions which are scarce (Rajeevan et al., 2008). The situation of growing urbanisation and land-use changes in changing rainfall intensity in Mumbai is also unexplored which is major limitation in flood mitigation and climate change adaption. Mumbai city is vulnerable due to low lying coastal area for changing climate and floods due to extreme precipitation (Mujumdar et al. (2020). The present study aims this with R programming language.

5. Literature Review

Increase in rainfall variability and extreme rainfall events is growing concern in the city like Mumbai. Some previous studies have analysed rainfall trends, variability, etc. The increase in rainfall intensity and monsoon unpredictability is related to changes in large scale climate pattern i.e., ENSO (Loo et al. 2015). Historical rainfall data in India shows significant rise in short duration, high intensity rainfall events, which can have intense urban flooding (Rajeevan et al. 2008). To study extreme and severe climate, appropriate trend indices are useful to do studies over cities like Mumbai (Mann et al. 2023). Several studies are carried out on the urbanization and its role on changes in rainfall. Urban heat island creates convective activity which increases heavy rainfall events (Steensen et al. 2022). This study suggests that there is need of long-term monitoring to understand the extreme rainfall events.

Statistical techniques are widely used in rainfall trend analyses. According to Aditya et al. (2021) Mann-Kendall trend analyses are useful to detect the rainfall trends and its variability. According to Kumar et al. (2020) statistical analyses of long-term rainfall trends in India shows increase in rainfall and seasonal variability. The R programming language is helpful to process the large rainfall data to understand the hidden complexity in the dataset. Multi Resolution Analysis (MRA) and Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) can model rainfall dataset and can predict extreme events (Garai et al. 2023, Sashank et al. 2023). Mann and Gupta (2023) have analysed rainfall data with geospatial technology and found that spatial analyses can be effective in rapidly growing urban regions. These studies indicates that statistical methods, programming languages, and GIS analyses gives understanding to rainfall variability and its extreme events.

6. Research Methodology

Present study focuses with daily rainfall pattern in Mumbai from 2010 to 2019. It studies rainfall variability, rainfall characteristics, and climate change detection. The daily rainfall in millimetre is obtained from Indian Meteorological Department (IMD).

In the methodology, first step was carried out on reading, cleaning, and pre-processing of the dataset using R programming. The date column was converted to require date format with lubridate package and missing values converted to zero. The complete sequence of the dataset was prepared from June 01, 2010, to September 30, 2019. In the present study the data is used for the months of June, July, August and September. First exploratory data analyses were carried out to understand the distribution and seasonality of the rainfall. We have computed descriptive statistics measures such as mean, median, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation. Further rainfall totals were aggregated on month wise and year wise. Next to these graphical visualizations i.e., daily rainfall trends, time series plots, box and whisker plots of monthly rainfall, bar charts of annual rainfall with regression trend lines, etc. carried out. Further potential climate change evidences were detected with long-term rainfall trends. The analyses include; trend detection with Mann-Kendall test to detect increasing or decreasing trends. The 5-year moving average was used to smooth the variation to observe long term trend. The days with rainfall above 95 percentiles are identified as extreme rainfall events. The extreme rainfall events are analysed to understand the change in observed heavy rainfall.

The present study analysed rainfall variability, its characteristics, and climate change impact in Mumbai using R programming. The methodology used includes statistical techniques, trend analyses, extreme rainfall assessment to understand cities changing climate. The finding of the study will contribute to urban planning, flood management, and adaption to the climate change strategies. Further work may involve integration of temperature data. Study can be extended to climate projection and GIS and remote sensing based spatial analyses with rainfall.

7. Data Analysis and result

The following results and interpretations analyze rainfall variability, rainfall characteristics, and climate change evidences in Mumbai from 2010 to 2019 with R programming.

1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
0	0	7.298	0.625	375.2

Table 1. Summary statistics.

The summary statistics in Table 1 with Mumbai's daily rainfall data from 2010 to 2019 shows very high rainfall variability. The analyses are carried out for June, July, August and September for all the

ten years. More than half the days shows no rainfall. Some extreme events cover the total rainfall year wise. The maximum rainfall is 375.2 mm in one day. The mean daily rainfall is 7.3 mm which is skewed by intense rainfall occurrences. That suggests erratic pattern and extreme rainfall events. Such variability may be characterized by dry spells and extreme rainfall. These can lead to flooding and pose challenges of urban flooding. Therefore, further trend analyses are necessary.

Figure 1. Daily rainfall over time in Mumbai.

Figure 1 shows daily rainfall for Mumbai from 2010 to 2019. The inter-annual variability can be seen in the years such as 2013, 2017 and 2019. These years receive frequent and intense rainfall peaks which show extreme rainfall events. The recent years suggests more erratic situation of monsoon. This shows climate change indication. This suggests flood management strategies for the city.

Figure 2. Monthly rainfall trends in Mumbai.

The figure 2 shows monthly rainfall trends from 2010 to 2019. It can be clearly seen that rainfall increases in June, peaks in July and August and rapidly decreases in September. The observation on different years suggests that some year receives higher than usual rainfall in June to September. It shows changes in monsoon onset and withdrawal. The clear peaks in after 2015, is the indication of climate change with rainfall intensity.

Figure 3. Annual rainfall trends in Mumbai.

In figure 3, annual rainfall trend from 2010 to 2019 for Mumbai shows some year with for example 2011, 2015, and 2018 receives lower total rainfall, on the other hand years for example 2010, 2013, and 2019 received higher rainfall. The upper trend in red line in figure 3, shows slightly increases in year wise rainfall over the given period. Some years shows drops followed by gain in the rainfall. This shows that there is a need of steadily monitoring for the adoption of the changing climate for urban planning.

Figure 4. Trend analyses with 5-year moving average.

From figure 5, five year moving average can be seen for rainfall in Mumbai. The graph highlights precipitation variation for longer period of time. The grey peaks show individual rainfall. It is seasonal peaks. On the other hand, red smooth line is the longer trends. The increase in the red line shows little bit increase in average daily rainfall over time.

Test	S	varS	Kendall's Tau (τ)	z-value	p-value	Trend Significance
Mann-Kendall Trend Test	-1	125	-0.022	0	1	Not Significant

Table 2. The Mann-Kendall trend test results.

In table 2, the result shows the Mann-Kendall trend test results. The p-value of 1 in the result show no dominant increase or decrease in the trend for the given time. The test statistics S is -1 and Kendall's tau is -0.022 which are very close to zero. It confirms there is no trend. That means there is inter annual variability but long-term variability is absent. That means over given decade year wise rainfall is constant but within year there are fluctuations. But additional analyses on extreme rainfall events and seasonal shift are requiring to study and understand the climate change in the Mumbai.

Figure 5. Count of extrem rainfall days for Mumbai.

With respect to count of extreme rainfall days, the years 2010, 2016 and 2017 shows increase while 2013, 2015 and 2018 shows decrease. This shows that extreme rainfall events are not well distributed over the given decade. This may be due to changes in monsoon pattern, climate change or synoptic weather anomalies. The recurrences of intense rainfall observed after 2015 this suggests increase in the intense precipitation events. This suggests need of flood mitigation strategies in Mumbai.

Figure 6. Bar graph and trend line shows rainfall seasonality analyses for the month of June, July, August and September. It is one of the climate change indicators.

In the figure 6, higher rainfall totals can be observe in the year 2010, 2011, and 2019 whereas 2013, 2015, and 2018 show notable decrease in the total rainfall. The upward red trend line shows gradual increase in the rainfall over the given time period. This may link to the climate change and monsoon

pattern. This may include late onset, increase in the intensity in uneven distribution of the rainfall. The recent year rainfall patterns show the possibility of increasing in the precipitation events in the upcoming future.

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Coefficient of Variation (CV)	0.238	The value indicates moderate variability in annual rainfall.

Table 3. Rainfall variability based on coefficient of variation (2010–2019).

The coefficient of variation (CV) in table 3, of 0.238 shows moderate rainfall variability in Mumbai from in the given period of time. In the CV higher values indicated rainfall fluctuations on the other hand lower values shows consistent rainfall patterns. In this study the CV value is 0.238. This shows that Mumbai has year wise total rainfall variations. But at the same time overall distribution of the rainfall is stable. But this is not considered extreme rainfall events of seasonal changes. This is a challenging thing.

Figure 7. Box and whisker plot of monthly rainfall distribution of Mumbai.

In figure 7, the there are many outliers in June, July, August, and September which shows of extreme rainfall events, which have intense monsoon rainfall and climate variability. The distribution is skewed in terms of outliers. That show upredictability and need of flood preparations and need of water resources in the hiterland areas.

Statistic	Value (mm)	Interpretation
Minimum (Min.)	1823	This shows the driest rainfall year.
1st Quartile (Q1)	2255	25% of the years had annual rainfall below it.
Median (Q2)	2655	This shows a balanced distribution rainfall.
Mean	2665	The average is close to median means moderate variability.
3rd Quartile (Q3)	3102	75% of the years have rainfall below it.
Maximum (Max.)	3682	This is the wettest in the decade.

Table 4. Summary Statistics table of annual rainfall from 2010 to 2019 in the Mumbai.

The variability in rainfall can be seen in the summary statistics with year wise rainfall from 2010 to 2019 in Mumbai from table 4. The minimum rainfall is 1823 millimeter whereas maximum rainfall is 3682 millimeters. The median value is 2655 millimeter show balanced distribution. The mean which is 2665 millimeters is close to median rainfall value indicates balanced distribution of rainfall. The inter quartile range which is 2255 millimeter to 3102 millimeter shows the spread of the rainfall year wise. It can be seen that beyond this range show wet or dry years with rainfall.

8. Discussion and conclusion

The rainfall analyses using R programming for Mumbai city shows rainfall variability, seasonality and extreme rainfall events. The result of Mann-Kendall indicates no long-term significant trend in annual rainfall but on the other hand high intensity rainfall and extreme daily rainfall shows increasing monsoon variability patterns. The moving average of 5 year shows small increase in mean rainfall. It shows rainfall intensity changes and changes in its distribution throughout the give time period. The coefficient of variation reflects small inter-annual variability, whereas extreme rainfall days indicate fluctuating trends, this may due to climate change or urban influence. The finding suggests that total annual rainfall may remain stable but extreme rainfall event may increase in frequency and intensity.

The study reflects benefits of continuous rainfall monitoring and need of flood management strategies for risks associated with extreme rainfall events. The city Mumbai have vulnerability to urban flood, here the observed trend suggests improved drainage systems, urban water management, and climate change related planning. The suggestion for future research is inclusion of temperature data. Further GIS based analyses and planning can provide local flood risk output. The integration of R programming language in rainfall data analyses provides effectiveness in rainfall trend analyses, its variability and climate change recognition in the city Mumbai.

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